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“A STUDY ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS IN PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM PELVIC INFLAMMATORY DISEASE IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL”

Anju Paulose*, Bharathi D.R.¹, B. Shankar Reddy¹, Anju Arpana², Anto John¹, Anu Rajan¹, Rahul Jose¹, Y Satykrishna¹

¹Department of Pharmacy Practice, SJMCP, Chitradurga, Karnataka, India.

²Department of OBG, BMCH & RC, Chitradurga, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) constitute the Upper reproductive tract infection in women and a major health concern leading to profound gynaecological morbidity among women in reproductive age group with impact on individual women, their families and communities. These infections entail a heavy toll on women, if untreated they can cause long-term complications, such as tubal infertility, ectopic pregnancy, chronic pelvic pain and abortions. Objectives: To analyze and evaluate the rationality of prescribing pattern of AMAs in PID and to monitor the ADRs & drug interactions, if any, with AMAs & concomitant drugs. Materials and Methods: A six months prospective observational study was carried out at OBG In-Patient department of Basaveshwara Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Chitradurga. Results: A total of 85 patients were enrolled in the study aged above 18 years from the OBG In-Patient department. Coming to the prescription pattern of antibiotics Nitroimidazoles & Cephalosporin's were majority of 36.36% & latter with 29.54. Coming to the concomitant drugs, NSAIDs & antacids were major in proportions (7.24% & 44.15%). Coming to the combination of antibiotics mostly prescribed drugs were Nitroimidazoles + Cephalosporins (37.34%) & Nitroimidazoles + Fluoroquinolones(13.29%). Conclusion: This study concludes that Nitroimidazoles & Cephalosporins were the first line choice of antibiotics in PID either alone or combination of same. NSAIDs with the combination of Aceclofenac/Diclofenac with Camylofin were mostly preferred for relieving pain & antacids were co-prescribed with NSAIDs to avoid NSAID induced gastric irritation.

Corresponding author

Anju Paulose

Mukalath House,
Assamannoor PO, Odakkali,
Ernakulam Dist, Kerala State,
Pin: 683549. Phone: 9446889494
anjupaulose67@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

PID constitute the upper reproductive tract infection (URTI) in women and a major health concern leading to profound gynaecological morbidity among women in reproductive age group with impact on individual women, their families and communities.¹ These infections entail a heavy toll on women, if untreated they can cause long-term complications, such as tubal infertility, ectopic pregnancy, chronic pelvic pain and abortions.²

Although data is available worldwide regarding the pattern of antimicrobial usage in PID patients, such data is relatively scarce from a developing country like India especially from the eastern part of our country. Hence, this prospective study was undertaken to understand the pattern of antibiotics usage among PID patients in rural teaching hospital of India.³

Objectives of the study are to analyze and evaluate the rationality of prescribing pattern of AMAs in PID and to monitor the ADRs & drug interactions, if any, with AMAs & concomitant drugs.

METHODOLOGY

This study was a prospective observational study for a period of six months from October 2015 to March 2016 which was conducted at OBG in-patient department of Basaveshwara Medical College & Hospital, Chitradurga.

The female patients aged 18-70 years suffering from Pelvic Inflammatory disease attending OBG department of Basaveshwara Medical college & Hospital, Chitradurga were enrolled & who were on antimicrobials and satisfy the inclusion and exclusion criteria were recorded in a suitably designed data collection form. The study was carried out with proper approval from Institutional Ethics Committee of Basaveshwara Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Chitradurga.

The study was analyzed by using Statistical package for social service (SPSS) 19th version. Descriptive statistics tools were used to describe the data. Categorical data was presented as frequency and percentage.

RESULTS

Age wise distribution

A total of 85 prescriptions were analyzed during the 6 months study period. The maximum numbers of female patients suffering from Chronic PID were from the age group of 35-55 years and least of the patients fall under age group of 55-70 yrs. (Figure-1).

Figure 1: Age wise distribution.

Number of antimicrobials prescribed

During the study, it was observed that the most commonly prescribed Antimicrobial agents were Nitroimidazoles followed by cephalosporins, anthelmintics, fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides. Tetracyclines were the least prescribed class. (Figure: 2).

Figure 2: Number of antimicrobials prescribed.

Combination of antimicrobials prescribed

Individually, most commonly used agents of these is Nitroimidazole + Cephalosporins 59 (37.34%), followed by Nitroimidazole + Fluoroquinolones 21 (13.29%), Nitroimidazoles with Aminoglycosides 16 (10.12%) and least prescribed was Nitroimidazoles + Cephalosporins + anthelmintics + Fluoroquinolones (Figure -3).

Figure -3: Combination of antimicrobials prescribed

Concomitant drugs used

In the concomitant medications, NSAIDs 70 (37.24%) were mostly prescribed followed by Antacids 83 (44.15%) as a co-prescription for NSAIDs induced gastric irritations. Sedatives were the least prescribed class (0.53%). (Figure- 4)

Figure- 4: Concomitant drugs used.

Route of drug administration

Out of Total 199 antimicrobials prescribed, n=146 (73.36%) were given parenterally and n=53 (26.64%) were orally administered (Figure - 5).

Figure – 5: Route of drug administration.

DISCUSSION

Drug utilization defined as the study of usage of drugs in the community or race. The drug utilization evaluation studies (DUEs) aims to analyse the rationality of drugs usage and also describes the nature and drug exposure, and may also help to identify non-adherence problems. Pelvic inflammatory disease is a major health concern leading to profound gynaecological morbidity among women in reproductive age group. Therefore this study was undertaken to analyze the prescription pattern of Antimicrobial Agents in patients suffering from Pelvic Inflammatory Diseases. The present study was a hospital based descriptive study conducted among subjects having PID, attending OBG department of a tertiary care hospital and mainly focused on prescription pattern among PID patients.

A study was conducted by Pyarelal *et al* , on A Prospective Study on Drug Utilization of Antimicrobial Agents in patients suffering from Pelvic Inflammatory Disease in a tertiary care teaching hospital. Their studies emphasized that the cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gynaecology & Obstetrics of Rama Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Hapur; for a period of one year. A total of 442 prescriptions of clinically diagnosed Pelvic Inflammatory Diseases cases from Outpatient Department .Average number of antimicrobial agents per prescription was 2.0. Majority of patients were prescribed Antifungals (n=237, P=25.90%) followed by Nitroimidazoles (n=184, P=20.10%), Fluoroquinolones (n=182, P=19.89%), Doxycycline (n=166, P=18.14%), and least prescribed was Aminoglycoside and Urinary antiseptics (n=4, P=4.04%).² As compare with our study a total of 85 prescriptions of clinically diagnosed PID cases from inpatient , OBG department of the Hospital were collected and analysed on the basis of CDC and PEACH study. Most of the antimicrobials were administered parenterally and oral administration was less preferred. Majority of the patients were prescribed with Nitroimidazoles (n=80 , P=36) , followed by Cephalosporins (n=69, P=29) , Anthelmintics (n=27 , P=12) , Fluoroquinolones (n=22, P=10), tetracyclines (n= 11 , P=5), Aminoglycosides (n=15 ,P=6). And least prescribed drug was tetracyclines (n= 11, P=5).

A study was done by Basu J et al, Prescribing Pattern of Antimicrobial Agents in Pelvic Inflammatory Disease at a Rural Teaching Hospital in India. Cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gynecology & Obstetrics of MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar; for a period of one year. Average number of AMAs per prescription was 3.007. Majority of patients received oral Doxycycline 500(78.37%) in combination with Metronidazole followed by Ofloxacin 138(21.63%) with or without Metronidazole through oral and/or Intravenous (I.V) route. Gentamicin was prescribed in 17(2.66%) cases. Clotrimazole was prescribed topically in all patients.⁴¹ In our study, Majority of the patients received Antimicrobials with the combination of Nitroimidazoles. In that Nitroimidazole + Cephalosporins combination was used more, followed by Nitroimidazole + Fluoroquinolones. Nitroimidazoles + Cephalosporins + anthelmintics + Fluoroquinolones combination were used very least the total of 85 patients. A study conducted by Misra A et al, on Prescribing Pattern of Antimicrobials in the In-Patients Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital at Nepal. A prospective study was conducted by audit of prescriptions in the in-patients of obstetrics and gynecology department. Data collected on a specially designed proforma consisted of patient and treatment details. Number of prescriptions for a particular drug was used to express the prescribing frequency of that drug. Fixed dose combinations were counted as one. Data was analyzed to find out the pattern of diseased condition in women and prescribing pattern of AMA using WHO indicators. Ampicillin was the most frequently prescribed AMA followed by Metronidazole, Cefazoline, Gentamicin, Cefotaxime and Ciprofloxacin.¹⁶ In our study, the prescription pattern of the drugs were analysed on the basis of CDC guidelines. Nitroimidazoles were the most frequently prescribed AMA followed by Cephalosporins, Anthelmintics, fluoroquinolones. Tetracycline was the least prescribed drugs.

Sharma S conducted a study on, Drug Utilization Study in Pelvic Inflammatory Disease in A Teaching Hospital in North India. In the concomitant medications Antacids and supplementary drugs were mostly prescribed (n=68, P=31.19%) followed by NSAIDs (n=35, P=16.05%), Antiemetics (n=32, P=14.05%). Sedatives were the least prescribed class (n=15, P=6.88%). Out of Total 252 antibiotics prescribed all antibiotics were given orally, no parental administration. ⁴ In our study, we found that in the concomitant medications Antacids (n= 81, P=43) followed by NSAIDs (n= 70 , P=37) were prescribed more and sedatives(n= 1, P=0.53) were the least prescribed class. Out of total 85 patients, most of them were prescribed with intravenous route of administration of Antibiotics followed by oral route.

CONCLUSION

According to the analysed results and from view of literature, the conclusions made are;

- The age group of 35-55 were seen more in the study
- Nitroimidazoles followed by Cephalosporins were the most commonly prescribed AMA.
- Antacids and NSAIDs were the most frequently prescribed concomitant drugs in the total population
- Nitroimidazoles + Cephalosporin combination were seen more in the prescriptions followed by Nitroimidazoles + Fluoroquinolones.

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The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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